

Comparative transmission of three tungro isolates by green leafhopper (GLH)

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We studied the transmission of three tungro isolates obtained from the Philippines, Malaysia, and India by a Philippine GLH population. Adult GLHs fed for 3 d on plants of rice cultivar TN1 infected with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) of the isolates. The GLHs then fed for 1 d on nearly 2-wk-old seedlings of 12 rice cultivars using mass inoculation at about 4 insects/seedling.

In another experiment, we determined the reaction of these cultivars to RTBV using agroinoculation. Test plants were injected, 15-20 d after sowing, at the base of their stems with 50 µl of a viscous suspension of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* A₄ (pRTRB 1162) using a Hamilton microsyringe.

About 4.5 d after inoculation, we compared the test plants with the uninoculated control plants to determine reduction in plant height, leaf discoloration, and RTBV and RTSV infection, which was monitored by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. The relative concentrations of RTBV-DNA in agroinfected plants was determined by nucleic acid hybridization method using ³²P-labeled full-length cloned RTBV DNA (pJIIS2).

The transmission profiles of RTBV and RTSV either singly or together varied between the isolates. The Indian isolate produced higher proportions of doubly infected plants on cultivar TKM6 than did the other isolates. The Malaysian isolate produced more doubly infected plants on cultivars ASD7, Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, Balimau Putih, and TKM6 than did the Philippine isolate. The Malaysian isolate also produced more severe yellow-orange leaf discoloration on cultivar ASD7 than did the Indian isolate, which was more severe than the Philippine isolate. Agroinfected RTBV plants of cultivars ASD7 and Ptb 18 produced the most severe yellow-orange discoloration.

Reaction of 12 rice cultivars to RTRV and relative concentration of RTRV-DNA in agroinoculated plants.

Cultivar	Reaction ^a to		Reaction to RTBV by agroinoculation ^d (% infection)	RTBV-DNA concentration in plants relative to that in TN1 ^e
	GLH ^b	Tungro ^c		
ASD7	R	I	S	High
Ptb 18	R	I	S	High
ARC 11554	R	R	S	Low
Gampoi 30-12-15	R	R	S	Intermediate
Pankhari 203	MR	R	S	Low
Utri Merah	S	R	I	Low
Utri Rajapan	S	R	S	Low
Blimau Putih	S	R	I	Low
Vikrmanarya ^f	-	R	S	-
FK135	S	S	S	-
TKM6	S	S	S	High
TN1	S	S	S	N/A

^a IRR1 data. ^b Based on seedling damage rating (IRRI). ^c Based on percentage infection in mass inoculation in cages. ^d I (intermediate) = 31-60%. S. (susceptible) = more than 61%. ^e Low = less than 20%. intermediate = 20-40%. high = more than 41%. -, = not determined, N/A = not available. ^f Dr. A. Gosh. Hyderabad. India, pers. comm.

Results showed that most of the cultivars that appeared resistant by leafhopper inoculation were apparently susceptible by agroinoculation (see table). Except for two GLH-susceptible cultivars, Utri Merah and Balimau Putih, plants infected with RTBV by agroinoculation fell into the susceptible category. The relative concentration of RTBV-DNA in Utri Merah, Balimau Putih, Utri Rajapan, ARC11554 was low, while that in TN1, ASD7, Ptb 18, and TKM6 was high.

Our results provide additional evidence that Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, Balimau Putih, ARC 11554, and Gampoi 30-12-15 show some resistance to RTBV when inoculated by GLH. But on agroinoculation, only Utri Merah and Balimau Putih show any resistance. Thus, agroinoculation is a promising technique for determining true resistance in rice while avoiding the effect of leafhopper resistance. □

Dependence of incubation period and symptoms of rice tungro disease (RTD) on infection stage in ricefields

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For both field epidemiological studies and management of RTD, it is essential to estimate when and how many hills were infected. Diagnosis based on visible symptoms is often the most practical method to quickly survey fields. To improve visual diagnosis, we studied how incubation period and duration of RTD symptoms are affected by infection stage.

Experiments were laid out in a field at Celuk Field Laboratory, Bali, late 1989 in the dry season when RTD occurrence was negligible. Variety Krueng Aceh was transplanted 21 d after sowing. For inoculation in the field, one outer stem of

a hill was inserted in a glass tube, supported by an erect stick. A *Nephotettix virescens* adult was released in it for 1 d after 1 d of access to RTD-diseased hills. Inoculation 1 d before transplanting (DBT) was made in test tubes. We observed plants daily for 5 wk. We graded symptoms and confirmed diagnosis by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay test.

The incubation period was positively correlated with the infection stage except at 1 DBT (see table). The infection at 1 DBT showed inconspicuous, pale-yellow discoloration, and prolonged duration of incubation, Gr. 1, and Gr. 2. Plants infected at 1-5 wk after transplanting (WT) developed the typical leaf-yellowing symptoms. Duration of Gr. 3 for those infected at 1-3 WT lasted less than 2 wk. Stunted leaves remained the only visible symptom after the yellow ones dropped off.

As healthy plants covered infected ones in the same hill, it became difficult to detect infection unless symptom records were available. In contrast, leaf yellowing at 5 WT lasted until 10 WT when the